

Project EARTHONE launches to transform and optimise natural environments

Madrid, Spain – The European initiative, EARTHONE: Environmental Analysis and Resilience for Transformative Human-Optimised Natural Environments, officially launched on January 1, 2025, held its kick-off meeting on January 22–23, 2025, at the Polytechnic University of Madrid. Bringing together experts and stakeholders from across Europe, the project is set to address the pressing challenge of preserving and enhancing Earth's natural terrestrial greenhouse gas (GHG) sinks, while fostering sustainable and resilient land-use practices.

About EARTHONE

EARTHONE's mission is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic, demographic, and physical drivers that influence GHG fluxes. The project adopts an innovative interdisciplinary approach, combining advanced data-driven technologies with on-the-ground data from vulnerable regions in southern and Mediterranean Europe, including Croatia, Greece, Italy, North Macedonia, Slovenia, and Spain.

Over the next four years, EARTHONE will work to develop multi-tiered solutions that address land use, land-use change, and forestry challenges. By employing regional pilots, the project will deliver evidence-based recommendations, adaptable methodologies, and policy guidelines for a diverse group of stakeholders, including landowners, environmental experts, and policymakers.

The partners

The EARTHONE consortium comprises 17 partners from 10 European countries, including research institutions, universities, technology companies, and land management organisations: [Universidad Politécnica de Madrid](#) (Spain), [Panepistimio Thessalias](#) (Greece), [GIS Gozdarski Institut Slovenije](#) (Slovenia), [AG Futura Technologii DOOEL Skopje](#) (North Macedonia), [OIKON DOO – Institut za Primijenjenu Ekologiju](#) (Croatia), [Agenzia Veneta per l’Innovazione nel Settore Primario](#) (Italy), [Università degli Studi di Padova](#) (Italy), [Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos – DIMITRA](#) (Greece), [Uczelnia Łazarskiego](#) (Poland), [Fondazione Medes](#) (Italy), [Australo Interinnov Marketing Lab SL](#) (Spain), [Universiteit Twente](#) (Netherlands), [The Cyprus Institute](#) (Cyprus), [Universität Bremen](#) (Germany), [EXUS Software Monoprosopi Etaireia Periorismenis Evthinis](#) (Greece), [Sistemas Avanzados de Tecnología SA](#) (Spain), and [Cedars, Svetovanje, D.O.O.](#) (Slovenia).

Benefits and expected outcomes

EARTHONE’s methodologies aim to reduce the gap in carbon sequestration and emissions, supporting progress toward the EU’s 2030 climate goals and 2050 carbon neutrality targets. The scalable solutions developed by the project will enhance resilience in land use and environmental management, ensuring the sustainable preservation of Europe’s natural GHG sinks while mitigating socio-economic and environmental risks.

EARTHONE on social media

[LinkedIn](#)

[X](#)

[Bluesky](#)

[YouTube](#)

For more information about EARTHONE, please contact:

Silvia Alba Uribe Mayoral
Project Coordinator
Email: silviaalba.uribe@upm.es

Julia Colomer
Project Dissemination and Communication Manager
Email: julia@australo.org

